

OPPORTUNITIES TO USE INNOVATIVE APPROACHES AND METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This article discusses the creative approach, the use of various methods and its effectiveness in teaching and learning foreign languages.

Key words: innovative technologies, pedagogical innovation, foreign language, “useful English”.

ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ПОДХОДОВ И МЕТОДОВ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННЫМ ЯЗЫКАМ

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается творческий подход, использование различных методов и его эффективность в обучении и изучении иностранных языков.

Ключевые слова: инновационные технологии, педагогические инновации, иностранный язык, “полезный английский”.

In accordance with the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to increase the quality of pedagogical education and further develop the activities of higher educational institutions training pedagogic personnel” “Systematic development of higher educational institutions training pedagogic personnel and their management to improve its activities, to develop modern educational programs with the introduction of advanced foreign experiences, to raise the training of highly qualified professional personnel to a new level, as well as to ensure the harmony of education, science and practice in the field of pedagogy” set as a goal.¹ According to it, it was determined that a graduate of the higher education institution who intends to continue continuous education must have a degree certificate in a certain foreign language if he intends to continue the master’s degree.

In the current era of globalization, researching innovative educational technologies and their pedagogical foundations, researching ways to effectively use modern interactive teaching methods in the educational process remains one of the urgent problems of today.

The socio-pedagogical necessity of an innovative approach to education is measured by the following:

1. Scientific-technical progress and socio-economic renewal of the continuous education system, in particular, the study of advanced foreign experiences of the educational process in educational institutions, improvement in education using innovative approaches and information technologies;

2. Creation and implementation of effective organizational forms and technologies of person-oriented education that serve to develop the level of education, intellectual potential, social activity, and creativity skills of students;

3. The need to develop the professional-innovative competence of the teacher in relation to mastering and implementing pedagogical innovations².

¹ <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-6079561>

² Ibragimova Sh. The need to use innovative technologies in the process of teaching foreign languages

Effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process and the introduction of modern innovative technologies into the educational process are improving the quality and efficiency of education. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. Innovative technologies are of great importance in language learning and teaching.

The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, writing, listening, speaking). For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. It is known that the lesson is conducted on the basis of various games, which allows students to demonstrate their abilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger.³

In the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach students to think independently. Today, English language teachers are using the following innovative methods based on the experience of pedagogues in the United States and England.⁴:

- To apply this method of “Creative Problem Solving”, the beginning of the story is read and the end of the story is referred to the judgment of the students;
- “Merry Riddles” teaching riddles to students is important in teaching foreign languages, they learn unfamiliar words and find answers to riddles;
- “Quick answers” helps to improve the efficiency of the lesson;
- “Warm-up exercises” using various games in the group to interest students in the lesson;
- “Pantomime” (pantomime) this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when students are tired when written exercises are done.

As a result of the use of such methods in learning foreign languages, the ability to think logically and critically develops, the speech becomes fluent, and the ability to answer quickly and correctly is formed.

Technical means to improve the quality of education: audio-video, film materials, computers, video projector, slides, excerpts from works of art; modern pedagogical technologies, in particular interactive methods, are used appropriately. Innovative educational technologies improve the quality of education, increase its effectiveness, establish mutual cooperation between the team, achieve ideological and spiritual unity, strive for a single goal, realize the internal potential of each learner, is considered to have great potential in creating the necessary conditions and environment for its manifestation as a person.

We offer a creative platform (site) called “Useful English” in order to use innovative approaches and methods in teaching foreign languages. This program includes subtitled movies, animated grammar, and the creation of shows using polyglot.

We learn English using creative methods in the mobile application. That is,

1. The audio of the given exercises is played on a gramophone (animation);
2. Uzbek folk tales are translated and discussed;
3. A QR code is placed for each audio and video tutorial;

³ MD Ismatullaevna, EG Yusupovich. the effectiveness of the use of information technology in the educational _rocess- european journal of research and reflection in ..., 2019

⁴ <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/zitdmrt/article/view/5280>

4. Each exercise and video will be in animated form, which will motivate the listener and make it easier to learn more effectively;

5. A bot channel is launched in Telegram. This will create an opportunity to learn the opinion of users.

The next stage is subtitled films. In this case, Uzbek and foreign films are translated, placed in the application and shown via QR code. The movies will have subtitles and through it the listener can improve their pronunciation even more. The creativity is that after each film, the new words used in it are given in the form of a dictionary.

At present, it has become somewhat difficult to attract young people to any useful work. They can be interested in a certain process only by giving them strong motivation. The task is to interest young people in remote areas in learning foreign languages. It is known that television is a great power. That is, attracting young people through TV shows. For example, an artist who has achieved great success in his field, cinema creator or sports master. Of course, there are many supporters of them, especially young people make up the majority of this group. A program is prepared in which the stars are taught 16 lessons of English by a qualified specialist. By themselves, young people are more inspired to learn a foreign language through their idol. Based on interest, the number of such classes will continue to increase.

In conclusion, it should be said that as a result of using innovative methods in English language classes, the ability to think logically and critically develops, the speech becomes fluent, and the ability to answer quickly and correctly is formed. Such creative methods instill a passion for knowledge. This makes students active subjects of the educational process.

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